

Reading the Landscape: Data Extraction Using Computer Vision for the Artemis Project

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1 Introduction

The Scheldt Valley between Antwerp and Ghent faces wetland loss and urban expansion [1, 2]. Understanding historical landscape change is essential for informed environmental management, yet crucial cartographic evidence remains fragmented across archives and institutions. This paper presents the initial results of the Artemis project, which develops open digital infrastructure for historical maps of the Scheldt River Valley. With Artemis, we demonstrate how computational methods can transform archival cartographic materials into research-ready datasets that address contemporary environmental challenges. Our work brings together humanities research and computer vision to enable scalable and systematic analysis of historical maps.

Our corpus comprises materials documenting the Scheldt floodplain from the fifteenth through the nineteenth century. Major series include Ferraris (1770–1778), Primitive Cadastre (1808–1844), Vandermaelen (1846–1854), and Reduced Cadastre (1847–1855), supplemented by handwritten local maps and specialized atlases. These collections exhibit heterogeneity in scale, quality, graphic conventions, and degradation levels, posing substantial challenges for automated processing.

The processing pipeline consists of four stages. First, selected maps are hosted via IIIF and georeferenced using the Allmaps platform¹. Second, toponyms on the map are detected via MapReader [3] and disambiguated using the Belgian Historical Gazetteer [4]. Third, land use and other important geographical features are detected on the maps. Finally, the extracted metadata will be corrected and published as linked open data and accessible on the Scheldt Mapped Viewer. In this paper, we focus on two computer vision components within this broader pipeline: text recognition and parcel-level segmentation for the Primitive and Reduced Cadastre maps, corresponding primarily to the detection and extraction stages of the workflow.

¹<https://allmaps.org/>

2 Methods

2.1 Parcel boundary segmentation and extraction

The Belgian Primitive Cadastre, archived at the State Archives of Belgium², records the earliest systematic parcel boundaries and property identifiers, making it a foundational source for reconstructing historical land ownership and land-use patterns. Segmenting these parcels and detecting their associated numbers is therefore essential for linking spatial units to archival records. We annotated parcel polygons on 9 Primitive Cadastre map sheets using LabelStudio³. These maps form a manually annotated subset, with one sheet reserved for validation and the others used for training. As annotated cadastral data are still being progressively collected, this setup provides an initial evaluation of parcel boundary extraction on this map series. Each map was converted into a segmentation mask by rendering the polygons with a predefined stroke width. We fine-tuned a UNet++ model [5] to segment map contours and compared it with the Mask2Former-based historical map segmentation model from R. Petitpierre [6]. Each map was tiled into 512×512 patches, and patch-level outputs were merged back into full-sheet masks after inference.

On the validation map sheet, the fine-tuned UNet++ model achieved a Dice score of 0.633 and an IoU of 0.463, slightly outperforming the Mask2Former-based map segmentation model (see Table 1). Figure 1 provides a visual comparison of the two models on the validation set. The low IoU scores illustrate the difficulty of accurate contour segmentation, although the predicted contours remain useful for downstream polygon extraction after post-processing. While the generic Mask2Former-based model [6] was more consistent, it also segmented additional non-boundary lines.

Table 1: Full-map segmentation performance of the fine-tuned UNet++ model and the Mask2Former-based model [6] on the Primitive Cadastre validation set.

Model	Dice score	IoU
Fine-tuned UNet++ model	0.633	0.463
Mask2Former-based model [6]	0.616	0.445

After segmenting the parcel contours on the map, we can extract polygons from the predicted boundaries. However, small gaps and breaks in these contours lead to incomplete polygons. To mitigate this, we applied a lightweight post-processing step using morphological closing to repair the small gaps. This simple operation substantially improved the polygon extraction. Figure 2 visualizes the extracted polygon parcels on one of the cadastral maps.

²<https://www.arch.be/>

³<https://labelstud.io/>

Figure 1: Patch-level results for cadastral parcel segmentation. (a) original patch, (b) ground-truth mask, (c) UNet++ prediction, (d) Mask2Former-based prediction [6].

Figure 2: Polygon extraction results on one Primitive Cadastre sheet. Most parcels are detected, while fragmented boundaries highlight the current limitations of the pipeline.

2.2 Text Recognition

For both cadastral map series, text was annotated using the LabelStudio platform. The Primitive Cadastre maps contain many handwritten parcel numbers, while the Reduced Cadastre maps include only a small number of place names. We annotated 8 maps for the Primitive Cadastre containing 4000 words and 111 maps for the Reduced Cadastre containing 2530 words. Most words were simply annotated with a rotated bounding box instead of a tight polygon, as this was much more efficient. Additionally, our use case does not need a pixel perfect detection of each word.

We use this dataset to fine-tune the text recognition model in MapReader [3], and we compare the model’s performance with the MapTextPipeline pre-trained model [7] using the evaluation code from the ICDAR MapText Competition⁴. We found that the fine-tuned model greatly outperformed the pre-trained model for both series. The Character Error Rate (CER) is the most important metric to consider, which is calculated for all the correctly detected words. On the Reduced Cadastre maps, only toponyms were labeled, resulting in a poor score for F_1 and H-Mean for the pre-trained model due to the detection of background numbers and other small, non-target text. Table 2 lists the full evaluation results and Figure 3 shows some sample outputs for the Primitive Cadastre.

Table 2: Text recognition results on the validation set before and after fine-tuning the MapReader model. *Since only toponyms were annotated on the Reduced Cadastre maps, the pre-trained model yielded low scores because it detected numerous background numbers and other non-target textual elements.

Map Series	Model	F_1 score	Tightness	H-Mean	CER (%)
Primitive	Pre-trained	0.718	0.687	0.711	27.8
	Fine-tuned	0.942	0.750	0.894	2.13
Reduced	Pre-trained	0.186*	0.652	0.297*	14.0
	Fine-tuned	0.957	0.793	0.912	3.63

3 Discussion

Our initial results show strong potential, but also reveal challenges due to the complexity of historical cartography. Fine-tuning the text recognition model on a small subset of maps proved to be essential. The state-of-the-art pre-trained model was insufficiently accurate, particularly for the Primitive Cadastre, containing mostly handwritten digits. Fine-tuning not only improved the recognition accuracy but also reduced the detection of irrelevant background text on the maps, producing outputs that align more closely with our goals.

Contour segmentation on historical maps remains challenging, which was also noted by [6]. Boundary lines on historical maps are thin, degraded, and visually

⁴<https://github.com/icdar-maptext/evaluation>

Figure 3: Results of MapReader text recognition on a patch from the validation set: (a) pre-trained model, (b) fine-tuned model.

inconsistent, while our annotations (vector polygons) have no intrinsic line thickness. In addition, annotated polygon edges do not always align pixel perfectly with the cartographic lines beneath them. Annotating boundaries directly on the raster would yield more precise masks, and we aim to investigate this approach. However, polygon-based annotation is significantly faster and already produces the parcel-level outputs we desire. Additionally, we found that post-processing the segmentation masks to fix small gaps in the predicted contours greatly improved results.

Cartographic features reflect the landscape and environmental conditions that have changed over several centuries. Detected parcel boundaries do not automatically correspond to historical or ecological units, and automated extraction must therefore complement rather than replace expert interpretation. In practice, the current parcel outputs are already useful for supporting exploratory vectorization and for accelerating the identification of spatial units, even if some cases remain incomplete and require manual correction. We aim to expand semantic segmentation to additional features such as buildings, water infrastructure, and land-use categories to better support humanities-driven research questions.

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